

From simple beeps to complex sounds: Custom-designed sounds improve shuttle run test performance and perceived enjoyment

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ABSTRACT

This study evaluated whether custom-designed sounds enhance participants' performance and improve affective responses during the 20-meter shuttle run test (SRT) when compared to the traditional beep sound. Twenty-three individuals (24.8 ± 4.5 years) completed three SRTs on separate test days in a randomised, counterbalanced order. During the SRTs, participants were guided either by the traditional beep sound (stimulus A) or by two different customised sounds (stimuli B, and C). The total distance covered, peak heart rate, perceived exertion, attentional focus, and enjoyment were compared between the SRTs. A significant main effect was observed for the total distance covered during the SRT ($p = .004$), with greater distances covered during stimulus B compared to stimulus A ($p = .001$). A main effect was found for peak heart rate ($p = .012$), with higher heart rates observed for stimulus B than for stimulus A ($p = .032$). No significant effect was found for rating of perceived exertion ($p = .665$). For attentional focus, a main effect of condition emerged ($p = .023$) without significant differences between stimuli. Perceived enjoyment showed a main effect ($p < .001$), with greater enjoyment for stimulus B than A ($p = .002$) and C than A ($p = .010$). Custom-designed sounds enhanced performance, effort investment, and enjoyment, potentially improving SRT validity and perceptions of exercise testing.

KEYWORDS

Encouragement; audio stimuli; exercise testing; performance enhancement; affective responses

Introduction

Cardiorespiratory fitness is recognised as one of the most important risk factors for all-cause mortality (Barry et al., 2018; D. C. Lee et al., 2011), making its assessment critical for predicting and preventing health-related issues (Ross et al., 2016). Furthermore, its assessment serves as a broadly used indicator of the effectiveness of exercise and intervention programmes in both healthy individuals and clinical populations (Poole & Jones, 2017).

Cardiorespiratory fitness is typically assessed in a laboratory setting using graded or incremental exercise protocols performed to the point of volitional fatigue, with continuous monitoring of oxygen uptake throughout the test (Beltz et al., 2016). Although direct measurement of maximal oxygen uptake (VO_{2max}) in the laboratory is considered the gold standard for evaluating cardiorespiratory fitness, it is expensive, time-consuming, and technically complex (Liguori, 2021). Consequently, this method is not practical for field settings where large numbers of participants need to be assessed in a short period of time. In these contexts, more cost-effective field tests, such as the 20-meter shuttle run test (SRT) (Léger et al., 1988), are commonly utilised. The SRT is the most widely used field-based maximal exercise test and is regarded as a valid and reliable method for estimating cardiorespiratory fitness (Mayorga-Vega et al., 2015a; Nevill et al., 2021). Its progressive, multi-stage design closely simulates graded ergometer tests typically used in laboratory environments.

A key challenge in maximal exercise testing (e.g., SRT) is ensuring that participants exert maximal effort, as failure to do so can compromise test validity (Chitwood et al., 1997; Poole & Jones, 2017). In young and healthy individuals accustomed to pushing themselves to exhaustion, maximal exercise tests yield highly reproducible results (Chidnok et al., 2013; Mayorga-Vega et al., 2015b). However, this reliability may not be assured in exercise-naïve, less fit, overweight, older adults, and clinical populations who may lack the experience or motivation to push themselves to the point of exhaustion (Poole & Jones, 2017). This can lead to inaccurate results, potentially causing misdiagnoses and the development of unsuitable training or treatment recommendations. To mitigate this issue, various strategies have been implemented in exercise testing to encourage maximal effort. Beyond verbal encouragement, music has been used in both research and practice to capture attention, regulate mood, enhance arousal, and increase confidence and performance expectations (Chow & Etnier, 2017; Delleli et al., 2023; Hutchinson et al., 2015; Karageorghis & Priest, 2012; Midgley et al., 2018; Terry et al., 2020). Additionally, these encouragement strategies can assist individuals in distracting themselves from the discomfort associated with exertion, which can alleviate negative feelings during exercise and ultimately enhance their willingness to put forth maximum effort (Chow & Etnier, 2017).

Regarding the SRT, previous research has shown that verbal encouragement can significantly increase test performance (Neto et al., 2015). Similarly, a study by Lamoned

et al. (2021) found that integrating music tracks into the standard SRT audio file significantly improved performance outcomes. While these findings are promising and underscore the positive effects of verbal encouragement and music during testing, several significant challenges persist with these approaches. Ensuring consistent standardisation of verbal encouragement is particularly challenging. Although the content and timing of verbal cues may seem easy to regulate, factors such as tone, pitch, and volume are much more difficult to control (Ketelhut et al., 2025). Similarly, the use of music – specifically harmonic, rhythmic Western music – introduces its own complexities. For example, aligning pre-existing music with the incremental test protocol of the SRT can be challenging. Additionally, ensuring a clear delineation between the music and the orientation tone during the test poses difficulties. Furthermore, the incorporation of pre-existing music introduces uncontrolled elements such as lyrics, cultural connotations, or familiarity, which may have unintended and unpredictable effects on mood and emotions (Finnäs, 1989). In contrast, customised sounds provide a more neutral and scalable solution that can be easily tailored to the testing environment and context, offering limitless design possibilities. For the SRT, custom-designed sounds may present a promising approach for creating a functional, engaging, and immersive experience that integrates seamlessly with the test procedure.

A substantial body of research supports the use of sonification and auditory displays in exercise settings. Sonification – the process of converting data into sound – has been shown to improve movement precision, enhance efficiency, boost performance, and aid in motor control in both sports and rehabilitation contexts (O'Brien et al., 2020; Schaffert et al., 2019). However, to date, no studies have explored the effects of custom-designed sounds during the SRT.

This study is one of the first to evaluate whether custom-designed sounds can enhance participants' willingness to exert maximal effort and improve affective responses during the SRT. To achieve this, we compared the effects of two customised sound stimuli designed by expert sound designers and the original sound file for the SRT on the distance covered, peak heart rate, perceived exertion, attentional focus, and enjoyment during the test. Building on previous studies (Lamonedá et al., 2021; Neto et al., 2015; Schaffert et al., 2019), we hypothesised that the customised sounds would increase the distance covered during the SRT, lead to higher peak heart rates, and result in lower ratings of perceived exertion compared to the original sound file. Additionally, we anticipate that participants will adopt a more dissociative attentional focus and report greater perceived enjoyment during the SRT with the customised sounds.

Materials & methods

Study desing

The study was conducted at the Institute of Sports Science of the University of Bern, utilising a within-subject randomised

crossover design. The study adhered to Declaration of Helsinki and received approval from the Research Ethics Board of the Faculty of Human Sciences at the University of Bern (Nr. 3 December 2023). All participants provided written informed consent.

Participants

Male and female participants were recruited from February to April 2024 through personal contacts and advertisements sent via university mailing lists at the University of Bern. After initial contact, interested individuals received written information about the study and were assessed for eligibility. To qualify, participants had to meet the following criteria: (1) be 18 years of age or older, (2) engage in no more than 2 hours of regular exercise per week, (3) not participate in competitive sports, (4) provide written informed consent, and (5) have no pre-existing medical conditions that could pose a risk during physical exercise.

An a priori power analysis was conducted using G*Power (Version 3.1.2; Heinrich Heine Universität, Dusseldorf, Germany) for a repeated measures ANOVA (test family: *F*-tests). Considering a large effect size (0.3) (Neto et al., 2015) for total distance at an alpha level of .05, a sample size of 20 participants was deemed necessary to achieve a power of 0.8. An additional 4 participants (i.e., total of 24) were recruited to account for attrition and outliers.

Measures

Anthropometric parameters

The participant's body mass and body height were assessed wearing light clothes (i.e., shorts and a short-sleeved shirt) and barefoot. Body mass and body fat percentage was measured using a scale (BC-545 Innerscan, Tanita, Netherlands). Waist circumference was measured to the nearest 0.1 cm at the mid-point between the iliac crest and the lowest ribs. Body Mass Index (BMI) was determined by dividing weight in kilograms by the square of height in metres (kg/m^2). The Waist-to-Height Ratio (WHtR) was calculated by dividing waist circumference by height (waist circumference/height).

Physical activity behavior

The German version of the Godin Leisure Time Exercise Questionnaire (Godin & Shephard, 1985; Nigg et al., 2024) was used to determine self-report physical activity. This psychometrically robust measure assesses the frequency of mild, moderate, and vigorous exercise (Nigg et al., 2024). Based on the questionnaire responses, weekly minutes of moderate to vigorous physical activity (MVPA) were calculated.

Rating of perceived exertion

Participants' ratings of perceived exertion (RPE) were evaluated using the BORG-RPE scale (Borg, 1985) immediately following the SRT. This numerical scale ranges from 6 to 20 and includes verbal descriptors, where 6 represents 'no exertion at all' and 20 denotes 'maximum exertion'. The BORG-RPE scale is recognised as a reliable and valid tool for estimating exertion levels during exercise (Borg, 2004).

Enjoyment

The German version of the PACES (Jekauc et al., 2013), consisting of 16 bipolar statements, was used to measure perceived enjoyment directly after the SRT. On a 5-point bipolar scale, participants rated their feelings about the exercise they had just performed. The total score of the questionnaire ranged from 16 to 80, with higher scores indicating greater enjoyment. A mean score was calculated for each session by summing all values (reverse-scoring for negative items).

The questionnaire is considered a reliable and valid measurement instrument, with good internal consistency ranging from 0.92 to 0.93 (Jekauc et al., 2013).

Attentional focus

Attentional focus, categorised as association versus dissociation, was assessed using the Attention Scale developed by Tammen (TAMS) (Tammen, 2008). The attention scale is a bipolar scale consisting of a single item, with a range from 0, representing complete associative focus (i.e., 'internal focus: bodily sensations, heart rate, breathing, etc'), to 10, indicating complete dissociative focus (i.e., 'external focus: daydreaming, external environment, etc'). Participants were instructed to indicate their attentional focus just before the scale was presented.

Heart rate

Heart rate was continuously recorded during all tests using a heart rate monitor (H10 Polar Electro OY, Kempele, Finland). The peak heart rate was registered as the highest value obtained at the end of the test.

Procedures

Shuttle run test

During the test, participants were instructed to run back and forth between two markers placed 20 meters apart. Their pace was controlled by auditory signals played at set intervals. The initial running speed was 8.5 km/h, with the speed increasing by 0.5 km/h every minute. Participants were instructed to perform as many shuttles as they could. The test ended when a participant withdrew due to exhaustion or after two consecutive failures to complete a shuttle within the designated time. The total number of shuttles completed, and stages reached were recorded for each participant. No feedback or encouragement was given by the test personnel during the test. The sound stimuli were emitted using a Bluetooth loudspeaker (JBL Charge 5, Los Angeles, USA), positioned in the centre of the 20-meter course. The total distance covered was calculated based on the number of shuttles completed.

Stimulus design

The design process for the audio stimuli involved a collaborative effort between expert sound designers and exercise physiologists, utilising an iterative approach. Initially, a variety of sounds were generated by senior students from the Master 'Sound Design' at Zurich University of the Arts within an open yet systematic framework following the 'double diamond' model of design process (Banathy, 2013). This method facilitated the development of a controlled selection of contrasting

sound options, enabling thorough evaluation and comparison. Once the initial design proposals were established, they underwent a rigorous expert review (sound designer and exercise physiologist). Feedback from this evaluation played a crucial role in refining the sound stimuli. The process culminated in the creation of two distinct stimuli, each tailored with specific design variables. While each stimulus utilised the same sound components (samples), they were modified to align with the standard audio file of the SRT, aiming to minimise design variables for practical implementation. The primary goal was to preserve the original sound aesthetics and core elements of the initial design, including the perception of progression, sonic movement affordances, and auditory associations. A detailed description of the stimulus design can be found in Hug and Ketelhut (2024).

Stimulus A: 'Standard Beep'. This version uses the original SRT audio file. After the verbal introduction, the test starts with a simple beep tone sequence produced by a square wave oscillator, sounding three times at approximately 435 Hz, followed by a single beep at 232 Hz. A male voice then announces the level and first shuttle, which is followed by a beep at approximately 232 Hz. The beep for the next level is identical to the shuttle beep.

Stimulus B: 'Chime Swell'. In this stimulus, the beep tone of the original audio file is replaced with a percussive sound that combines metallic and wooden percussion elements with added delay and reverb. A continuous tonal pad plays throughout the SRT, gradually increasing in volume to lead to the impulse sound. This design is intended to reflect the physical sensation of accelerating and then abruptly stopping at the end of a shuttle, with the 'bounce' represented sonically by the delay. Additionally, the swelling sound conveys the duration of each shuttle, creating a sense of progression by increasing the pitch by one step in a major scale with each shuttle, returning to the initial pitch after an octave, while employing sonic techniques akin to the Shepard tone to enhance the perception of continuous progression.

Stimulus C: 'Game Wobble'. This stimulus substitutes the beep tone with a short five-note motif generated by a square wave oscillator similar to Stimulus A, but features a softer tonality achieved through slight filtering and temporal envelope adjustments. The motif is inspired by classic arcade game stinger melodies, with the hypothesis that it would create a gamified experience. Additionally, a rapidly wobbling sound, produced by modulating the pitch with a low-frequency oscillator whose speed gradually increases, is introduced at the transition between levels. This prominent marker of progress is expected to enhance the gaming association and boost motivation. The pitch in this stimulus also rises in a similar manner to Stimulus B, supporting the overall sense of progression. Brief excerpts of the audio stimuli are available for download under: <https://zenodo.org/records/11210685>.

Experimental exercise sessions

Participants attended the laboratory for three separate sessions, with a washout period of no less than 72 hours and no more than 10 days between visits. All sessions were scheduled for the same time of day. Before the sessions, participants were instructed to arrive at least 4 hours postprandial and to avoid

consuming caffeine, alcohol, or nicotine for 4 hours prior to the sessions. Additionally, they were advised to refrain from any intense physical activity for at least 24 hours before each test day.

During the three visits, participants performed a SRT while being guided by one of three different sound stimuli, presented in a randomised and counterbalanced order. The randomisation was carried out by the principal investigator using a random sequence generator from www.random.org. On the first day of testing, demographic information, physical activity levels, and anthropometric measurements were collected. Furthermore, participants were provided with instructions on the different questionnaires applied after the SRT to facilitate their completion after the test. After completing the SRTs in the three test sessions, participants filled out the respective questionnaires. All assessments were carried out by trained research staff who used the same equipment and followed standardised procedures. Each of the three tests was administered under identical physical conditions and by the same person, with the laboratory temperature maintained at $19.4 \pm 1.0^\circ\text{C}$, and the test performed on a polyvinyl chloride (PVC) floor.

Statistics

Data were analysed using repeated-measures analyses of variance (ANOVA), with condition as the within-subject factor. When sphericity was violated, the Greenhouse-Geisser correction was applied. For significant interactions, follow-up *t*-tests were conducted with Bonferroni adjustments to control for Type I error inflation due to multiple comparisons. Partial eta-squared (η^2_p) values were computed to estimate the effect sizes for the interactions, with the following thresholds: small effect ($\eta^2_p = .014$), medium effect ($\eta^2_p = .06$), and large effect ($\eta^2_p = .14$). Statistical significance was set at $p < .05$ (Cohen, 1988). Furthermore, the standard error of measurement (SEM) and minimal detectable change (MDC) at the 95% confidence level were calculated.

Results

One participant failed to complete all conditions, citing competing time demands as their reason. Thus, the final sample included 23 participants (11 women, 12 men), between the ages of 19 and 35 years. No adverse events were reported among the participants during the test sessions. Participants' characteristics are presented in Table 1. Regarding BMI, three participants were classified as overweight, and one participant was classified as obese. According to body fat percentage, 6 participants were classified as obese and two as overweight (De Lorenzo et al., 2003). In terms of WHtR, two participants were above the established health risk threshold of 0.5 (Ashwell et al., 2012) (Table 1). According to their minutes of MVPA, only 8 participants met the World Health Organization's physical activity recommendations of >150 minutes per week (World Health Organization, 2020). Seven (30%) of the participants had prior experience with the SRT. The repeated-measures ANOVA for the total distance covered during the SRT revealed a significant main effect of condition ($F(2,44) = 6.385$, $p = .004$, $\eta^2_p = .225$). Participants covered significantly greater distances during stimulus B compared to stimulus A ($p = .001$, $B = 1054 \pm 303$ m, $A = 966 \pm 272$ m). The observed mean difference between stimulus A and B exceeded the MDC, with 71.4% of participants exhibiting a meaningful difference (Table 2). No significant differences were observed between stimuli A and C ($p = .401$, $C = 1008 \pm 302$ m), or between stimuli B and C ($p = .249$) (Figure 1).

Regarding peak heart rate a significant main effect of condition was found ($F(2,44) = 4.867$, $p = .012$, $\eta^2_p = .225$). Follow-up pairwise comparisons revealed differences between stimuli A and B ($p = .032$, $A = 190 \pm 8 \text{ min}^{-1}$, $B = 193 \pm 8 \text{ min}^{-1}$). The observed mean differences between stimulus A and B were lower than the MDC, with 23.8% of participants exhibiting a meaningful difference (Table 2). No differences could be detected between stimuli A and C ($p = .863$, $C = 191 \pm 6 \text{ min}^{-1}$) and B and C ($p = .142$) (Figure 2).

Table 1. Participant characteristics.

Outcomes	Mean \pm Standard deviation
Age (years)	24.8 \pm 4.5
Body height (m)	1.69 \pm 0.08
Body mass (kg)	63.8 \pm 13.5
Body Mass Index (kg/m ²)	22.1 \pm 2.9
Body fat percentage (%)	25.7 \pm 4.6
Waist-to-height Ratio	0.45 \pm 0.05
MVPA (min/week)	172 \pm 158

MVPA= moderate to vigorous physical activity.

Table 2. Standard error of measurement (SEM) and minimal detectable change (MDC) for the main outcomes.

Outcomes	SEM	MDC95%	% Above MDC (A vs. B)	% Above MDC (A vs. C)	% Above MDC (B vs. C)
Total distance covered	15.36	42.57	71.4	52.4	52.4
Peak heart rate	1.98	5.29	23.8	14.3	9.5
Rating of perceived exertion	0.56	1.55	19.0	33.3	23.8
TAMS score	0.82	2.27	19.0	19.0	19.0
PACES score	2.29	6.34	42.9	38.1	0

MDC95%= Minimal detectable change at the 95% confidence level; % Above MDC= Percentage of participants who showed a change greater than MDC for comparison between stimuli.

Figure 1. Total distance covered during shuttle run tests with different sound stimuli. Note: ## = $p < .01$ main effect of condition, ** = $p < .01$ differences from stimuli A.

Figure 2. Peak heart rate attained during shuttle run tests with different sound stimuli. Note: # = $p < .05$ main effect of condition, * = $p < .05$ differences from stimuli A.

The analysis of RPE data revealed no significant main effect of condition ($F(2,44) = .411, p = .665, \eta^2_p = .018$). With respect to the TAMS score a significant main effect was evident ($F(2,44) = 8.348, p = .023, \eta^2_p = .158$). However, the post hoc tests revealed no differences between stimuli A and B ($p = .079, A = 4.26 \pm 1.60, B = 5.30 \pm 2.20$), A and C ($p = .079, C = 5.30 \pm 2.42$), and B and C ($p = 1.000$).

For the perceived enjoyment there was a significant main effect ($F(2,44) = 12.022, p < .001, \eta^2_p = .353$) with post hoc test revealing significant differences between stimuli A and B ($p = .002, A = 50.51 \pm 10.77, B = 57.22 \pm 8.17$) and A and C ($p = .010, C = 56.70 \pm 8.09$). The mean difference between

stimuli A and B was higher than the MDC, whereas the mean difference between stimuli A and C was lower than the MDC (Table 2). Additionally, 42.9% of participants exhibited meaningful differences between stimuli A and B, while only 38.1% showed relevant differences between stimuli A and C. No differences were detected between stimuli B and C ($p = 1.000$) (Figure 3).

Discussion

The primary aim of this study was to investigate whether custom-designed sounds can enhance performance and

Figure 3. Paces score after shuttle run tests with different sound stimuli. Note: ### = $p < .001$ main effect of condition, * = $p < .05$, ** = $p < .01$ differences from stimuli A.

improve affective responses during the SRT in a sample of low-active adults. The results clearly demonstrate a significant positive impact of the custom-designed sounds on SRT performance, as reflected by a large effect size and the mean difference exceeding the MDC. Participants covered a significantly greater distance during the SRT with stimulus B compared to the traditional beep sound (stimulus A). The results are in line with previous studies determining the effects of different encouragement strategies on performance outcomes during the SRT. Neto et al. (2015) demonstrated that verbal encouragement from a coach during the SRT significantly increased the distance covered by adolescents performing the test. Similarly, Pacholek (2023) reported a significant increase in the distance covered by both active and inactive young adults when verbal encouragement was provided every 60 seconds during the SRT. Lamedona et al. (2021) found that integrating music tracks into the standard SRT audio file significantly improved the total distance covered. Considering the relatively inactive nature of this cohort and the short interval between SRTs, training effects can be ruled out, as can habituation effects due to the counterbalanced randomized design. The higher test performance suggests that participants have exerted greater effort, which is crucial for ensuring the validity of the test.

Although peak heart rate during the SRT was significantly higher with stimulus B compared to stimulus A, suggesting that participants exerted more effort with stimulus B, the practical significance of this difference is limited, as only 23.8% of participants demonstrated a change exceeding the MDC, indicating that the observed difference may not be clinically meaningful for most individuals. Our findings are consistent with previous research (Neto et al., 2015; Pacholek, 2023), which also reported higher peak heart rates during the SRT when encouragement strategies were implemented. Interestingly, there was no significant difference in RPE between the stimuli, suggesting that participants exerted greater effort with stimulus B yet did not perceive it as such. These findings contrast with Lamedona

et al. (2021), who reported significantly higher RPE values when music was integrated into the SRT.

The positive effects of stimulus B on the distance covered may be attributed to the gradual swelling sound, which provides a clear auditory cue for the duration of each shuttle, likely promoting a more efficient pacing strategy. Additionally, the complex and engaging nature of the stimulus may have redirected participants' attention away from the discomfort associated with increasing physical exertion. According to the dual-mode theory (Ekkekakis & Brand, 2019), an accumulation of physiological parameters (e.g., blood lactate, oxygen consumption, heart rate) with increasing exercise intensity triggers a surge of discomfort, leading to the perception that continuing the activity is intolerable (Ekkekakis & Brand, 2019). This effect is particularly pronounced in individuals unaccustomed to vigorous exercise (Toulouse et al., 2021), often causing them to stop or end the test before reaching their physical limits (Midgley et al., 2017). Previous studies on encouragement strategies (e.g., music, verbal encouragement), suggest that external stimuli can redirect attentional focus, helping participants dissociate from the unpleasant sensations of exertion (Chow & Etnier, 2017; Jones & Ekkekakis, 2019). This dissociative effect likely arises because the perception and processing of these stimuli compete for the limited cognitive resources required to perceive exertion (Jones & Ekkekakis, 2019). The dissociative effect of external stimuli has primarily been demonstrated during moderate to vigorous intensity exercise (Hutchinson et al., 2015; Jones & Ekkekakis, 2019), but not during near-maximal or maximal exertion. It remains uncertain whether this effect can be sustained at these higher levels of intensity. In the present study, the higher peak heart rate observed, coupled with no differences in RPE during the SRT with stimulus B, supports the assumption of a dissociative focus. However, the findings from the TAMS questionnaire do not fully align with this assumption. Although a significant main effect of condition with a large effect size was noted, post hoc tests revealed only a borderline significant difference between stimuli A and B, as

well as between stimuli A and C. It is important to note that the TAMS was administered immediately after the SRT, capturing participants' overall sense of attentional focus rather than their focus during specific stages of the test. Future studies should explore whether the sound stimuli can sustain a dissociative focus for an extended duration, potentially delaying the onset of negative feelings and, as a result, postponing participants' decision to terminate the test.

Regarding enjoyment the participants reported a significantly higher PACES score during stimulus B and C compared to stimulus A. However, only the mean difference between stimuli A and B can be considered meaningful as it exceeded the MDC. The results align with Lamonedá et al. (2021), who also found higher enjoyment when integrating music into the SRT. It seems that not only music but also engaging sound stimuli are able to positively affect the test experience of the participants. In a previous publication (Hug & Ketelhut, 2024) evaluating the auditory user experience of the traditional sound file of the SRT and the customised sound files, participants reported the simple beep sounds of the traditional SRT audio file to be 'uninteresting', 'unpleasant', and 'not enjoyable'. Moreover, they associated these sounds with 'sports' and 'training'. In contrast, stimulus B was rated as 'highly pleasant' and 'fun', with participants reporting feeling 'energized' and 'motivated' by the sound. They also associated this stimulus with 'games', 'animated films', 'movies', or 'movement'. These associations may indicate a more engaging experience that diverted attention from the demanding nature of the test, ultimately enhancing enjoyment. The positive effects on perceived enjoyment are noteworthy, as creating a more enjoyable testing experience, can potentially enhance participants' overall perception of exercise tests. This could enhance their attitudes towards exercise (Ekkekakis et al., 2011; H. H. Lee et al., 2016; Rhodes & Kates, 2015), potentially leading to greater adherence to exercise interventions. However, since seven participants had prior experience performing the SRT with the traditional sound file, it could be argued that the customised sound file may have benefited from a novelty effect, which could wear off after performing the test multiple times.

Limitations

Several limitations should be recognised, as they may impact the interpretation of the study findings. First, participants completed the SRT individually to minimise external stimuli; however, since this test is designed for large groups, it would be valuable to explore the effects in a group setting in a future study. Second, the study focused on healthy individuals who were not engaged in excessive regular exercise or competitive sports, which limits the generalisability of the findings. Previous research indicates that personality traits can influence the perception and effectiveness of encouragement strategies (Chitwood et al., 1997). Specifically, individuals involved in sports, particularly competitive ones, tend to be less influenced by external encouragement strategies. Moreover, the included participants were relatively heterogeneous in terms of physical activity engagement and

anthropometric status, with one-third of the participants meeting physical activity guidelines and a few being overweight or obese. Future research with a more homogeneous sample or stratified analyses could help further clarify these effects. Lastly, the results are limited to the two sound stimuli. Future studies should explore a more diverse range of stimuli, adjusting for tempo and volume while also considering individual sound preferences, as these factors have been shown to influence outcomes in music-related research (Ouergui, Jebabli, Delleli, et al., 2023; Ouergui, Jebabli, et al., 2023; Patania et al., 2020).

Conclusion

In conclusion, the findings of this study indicate that, compared to the traditional beep sound guiding the SRT, customised sound stimuli can significantly enhance performance, increase peak heart rate, shift attentional focus, and improve post-exercise enjoyment. This may not only enhance the validity of the test, as participants exert greater effort but also helps standardise encouragement and may also positively influence their perceptions of exercise testing. The incorporation of sound stimuli can transform the traditionally mundane testing process into a more engaging and enjoyable experience. Compared to verbal encouragement and music, sounds may provide a more neutral and scalable solution that is less likely to compromise the integrity of the test. Given the limitless design possibilities in sound design, further research is needed to explore additional sound stimuli and compare various components to identify the most effective elements. Additionally, it would be valuable to assess whether these customised sounds can enhance the validity of the SRT.

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Data availability statement

The data supporting reported results can be obtained directly from the correspondent author.

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